

CLEANKER project: CO₂ capture in cement plant by Calcium looping process

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ABSTRACT

The cement industry is a key-sector for the reduction of CO₂ emissions. According to IEA and ZEP studies, cement industry should contribute to the largest CO₂ emission reduction through CCS in Europe, in order to meet the target of 2°C of global temperature increase. In addition to oxyfuel combustion and post-combustion solvent-based capture technologies, which have attracted most of the research efforts up to now, Calcium looping (CaL) is recognized as the most promising

emerging technology for CO₂ capture in cement plants. The process comprises two basic steps: (1) "carbonation" of CaO to form CaCO₃ in a reactor operating around 650°C; (2) oxyfuel calcination in a reactor operating at 920-950°C, which makes the CaO available again and generates a gas stream of nearly-pure CO₂.

The paper illustrate the advancement of the CLEANKER project, aimed at demonstrating the CaL concept in a configuration highly integrated with the cement production process, making use of entrained flow reactors and compare it's impact (CO₂ saving and cost increase) with innovative clinkers under investigation (CSA and Belitic clinker).

The core activity of the project is the design, construction and operation of a CaL demonstration system comprising the entrained-flow carbonator (the CO₂ absorber) and the entrained-flow oxyfuel calciner (the sorbent regenerator). This demonstration system will capture the CO₂ from a portion of the flue gas of a cement plant) operated by Buzzi Unicem, using as CO₂ sorbent the same raw meal used for clinker production.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cement production is responsible for about 8% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [Oliver JGJ 2016] and for about 27% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions from industrial sources worldwide [IEA 2011]. The cement industry is thus a key-sector for the reduction of CO₂ emissions. Around 60% of direct CO₂ emissions from the clinker burning process are due to the calcination of limestone (i.e. dissociation of CaCO₃ into CaO and CO₂). The balance is associated with the emissions from the combustion of heavy fuels, mostly needed to drive the endothermic calcination reaction. In addition, indirect emissions are also associated with the consumption of the electric power required by the process (e.g. grinding).

According to IEA and ZEP studies [IEA 2011, ZEP 2013], the cement industry is key to the achievement of the 2°C global temperature increase target (IEA 2DS scenario), since it should contribute to the largest CO₂ emission reduction through CCS in Europe.

The European cement industry is already involved in the development of innovative solutions for the production of hydraulic binders characterized by high performance and lower CO₂ emissions. The use of alternative fuels and the increased use of composite cements constitute the state of the art for the technology utilized in cement production besides the limitations imposed by authorities and standardization bodies which have developed rapidly over the last few years. Nevertheless, further efforts in innovation are necessary both with regard to the search for alternative clinkering materials and for the implementation of productive processes.

The main strategic directions regarding R&D and sustainability for the Cement industry consist of :

- Giving increased attention to the aspects of sustainability within cement plants with an action plan orientated to achieving lower CO₂ emissions, fewer accidents within the plant, and increased social acceptance of the cement plant
- Working at a material level lowering the clinker factor in cement by using alternative raw materials and utilizing alternative fuels
- Collaborating with the standardization committee in order to open the way for the standardization of new cements
- Developing novel cementitious binders
- Improving the knowledge related to durability issues regarding concrete
- Developing strategies for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS)

The goal of this paper is to compare the impact in terms of CO₂ saving and cost increase of the innovative clinkers (CSA and Belitic clinker) under development, with an innovative process developed for CO₂ capture, based on the Calcium looping process and which is expected to be demonstrated at TRL 7 by the CLEANKER project.. The CLEANKER (CLEAN clinKER production by calcium looping process) project (www.cleanker.eu) received EC support from October 2017 to September 2021 under the Horizon 2020 project called "Enabling decarbonisation of the fossil fuel-based power sector and energy intensive industry through CCS" (LCE 29 – 2017) to advance the integrated Calcium looping process for CO₂ capture in cement plants.

2. NOMENCLATURE

CaL	Calcium Looping
CC	Carbon Capture
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCUS	Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage
CSA	Calcium Sulphoaluminate cement
LHV	Lower Heating Value

TRL Technology Readiness Level

3. CARBON CAPTURE AND STORAGE

Carbon Capture and Storage is a crucial technology for reducing CO₂ emissions to a level consistent with the targets set by the Paris Agreement. In the IEA's '2 Degrees Scenario' (2DS), CCS accounts for 14% of the emissions reduction, while in the 'Beyond 2 Degrees Scenario' this value rises to 32% [I. Energy 2017]. The models which remove CCS from the portfolio of available options experience a significant rise in the overall mitigation costs [IPCC 2018]. CCS is expected to be extensively applied to industries characterized by high process emissions, which is the case of the cement industry [[I. Energy 2017][IPCC 2018]. For this sector, several capture technologies have been proposed. Amine-based chemical absorption was tested with a mobile capture unit in Brevik (Norway) between 2013 and 2016 [Bierge L. 2014], and it has been the technology adopted in the Baimashan cement factory in Wuhu (China), capturing 50,000 t CO₂ per year [IPCC 2018]. Oxyfuel combustion has been tested at a pilot-scale in the Dania (Denmark) plant [Gimenez M. 2014], and specific tests for oxy-fuel burners, calciners and clinker coolers have been carried out in the framework of the CEMCAP project [F. Carrasco-Maldonado 2016]. Calcium looping has been tested in the 'tail-end' configuration at 200 kWth scale on flue gases of cement kiln effluents [Arias 2016, Hornberger H. 2017]. The demonstration of the integrated configuration of calcium looping is the target of the CLEANKER project, while the demonstration of the direct separation capture technology is the aim of the LEILAC project [Leilac 2019].

The addition of CCS to an existing cement plant is expected to increase the cost of clinker by 30-60 €/tcl, which reflects on a cost of CO₂ avoided in the range 40-80 €/tCO₂ [CEMCAP 2016].

4. CLEANKER PROJECT

4.1 CLEANKER technology – Calcium Looping and its challenges

In addition to oxyfuel combustion and post-combustion solvent-based capture technologies, which have attracted most of the research efforts up to now, Calcium Looping (or carbonate looping) is recognized as another very promising emerging technology for CO₂ capture in cement plants [Abanades C. 2015]. Calcium looping is a regenerative process, which takes advantage of the capacity of calcium oxide-based sorbents to capture CO₂ at high temperatures. The process is divided in two basic steps:

- (1) the capture of CO₂ by "carbonation" of CaO to form CaCO₃ in a reactor operating at around 650°C; and
- (2) oxyfuel calcination in a reactor operating above 900-920°C, which makes the CaO available again and releases a gas stream of nearly pure CO₂.

CaL appears particularly promising for application in cement plants because:

- CaO sorbent originates from the same raw material used for clinker production. Therefore, no additional chemical substances are required with respect to the materials already used in the cement plant;
- The rotary kiln and the clinker cooler, two key units of the clinker production process, can be operated as in conventional plants and the retro-fitting of existing kilns may therefore be simpler;
- The adoption of entrained flow gas-solid reactors, commonly used in cement plants, is particularly suitable for this Calcium Looping configuration, because in such reactors the same finely ground raw material prepared for clinker production (CaO) can also be used for CO₂ absorption without additional milling requirements.

Two fundamental options have been proposed in literature regarding the integration of the CaL in cement kilns [Spinelli M. 2017, Atsonios K. 2015, Ozcan DC. 2013]. The first and most straightforward is the tail-end CaL process configuration, where the CaL reactors are placed downstream of the clinker burning line as a relatively independent unit and the carbonator treats the flue gas exiting the cement kiln preheater or the raw meal [De Lena E 2017]. The second option is the highly integrated CaL process configuration (Fig. 1), where the carbonator of the CaL process is integrated in the preheating tower of the clinker burning line [Spinelli M. 2018]. The carbonator treats the flue gas from the rotary kiln after relevant cooling and the calciner of the CaL process coincides with the cement kiln precalciner, which is operated in oxyfuel combustion mode.

Compared to the tail-end CaL configuration, which is based on the conventional fluidized bed CaL reactors, and has been demonstrated up to TRL6 [Arias B. 2017, Hornberger M. 2017] in the Cemcap project framework [CEMCAP 2016], the integrated CaL process with entrained flow reactors is less advanced. Fundamental knowledge needs to be developed on the performance of raw meal as a CO₂ sorbent, which appears to be highly influenced by the level of aggregation between Ca and Si compounds in the raw meal and by the calcination conditions [Alonso M. 2017, Pathi SK. 2013]. The fluid-dynamics of the carbonator under high solid to gas ratio also needs to be better understood to validate the reactor models currently developed with basic gas-solid contact relations [Spinelli M. 2018].

The fundamental knowledge generated by CLEANKER, together with the experience that will be gained in designing and operating the pilot plant will ultimately allow the definition of more reliable reactor models and to performing techno-economic analyses of full-scale CaL cement plants.

Fig. 1: Highly integrated CaL configuration in a cement plant

4.2 Objectives and approach of CLEANKER project

The core activity of the project is the design, construction and operation of a CaL demonstration system including the entrained-flow carbonator (the CO₂ absorber) and the entrained-flow oxyfuel calciner (the sorbent regenerator). This demonstration system will be connected to the Buzzi Unicem kiln of the Vernasca cement plant (Italy) and will capture the CO₂ from a slip stream of the flue gases from the kiln, using the same raw meal that is used for clinker production as a CO₂ sorbent.

Other activities will include: (i) the screening of different raw meals to assess their properties as CO₂ sorbents, (ii) reactors and process modelling, (iii) scale-up study, (iv) economic analysis, (v) life cycle assessment, (vi) CO₂ transport, storage and utilization study, (vii) demonstration of the complete

value chain, including mineral carbonation of waste ash with the CO₂ captured in the pilot system, (viii) exploitation study for the demonstration of the technology in an operational environment at pre commercial scale (TRL>7) and for its first commercial exploitation based on CO₂ transport and storage opportunities.

CLEANER will develop the integrated CaL process configuration, by building a demonstration plant that will be connected to the 1.3 Mt/year cement plant in Vernasca. The demonstrator aims at demonstrating the complete CaL loop composed of the entrained flow carbonator and the entrained flow oxyfuel calciner (Fig. 2). Several test campaigns are foreseen in different operating conditions and using different types of raw meals, which will be brought to the plant from other quarries.

Fig. 2: Integration of CLEANER demonstrator with the existing cement plant (Vernasca, Italy)

3.3 Implementation schedule

The implementation plan spans four years from October 2017 to September 2021. The first year will be devoted to the detailed design of the CaL demonstration system and extensive characterization of raw meals. The second year will be focused on the erection of the demonstrator. The last two years will see experimental campaigns, results analysis, evaluation of technology scale-up, economic analysis and LCA of the integrated system.

The project is running according to expectations. The main results of the first year have been the following:

- Modelling: heat and mass balances of the system have been evaluated for several relevant operating conditions, in order to support the design of the actual demonstrator.
- Engineering of the demonstrator: the detailed design of the reactor has been carried out with a final version of the drawing that will be used for the purchase of the equipment, obtaining the necessary authorisation, and the construction of the demonstrator.
- Raw meal characterization: experimental tests using Vernasca raw meal were carried out to estimate the kinetic rates of calcination and carbonation under conditions as close as possible to those expected in the demonstrator.
- Assessment of regional and national regulations: regulations related to CCUS technology and their national implementations are compared for five countries (Italy, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Russia) involved in the planned CCUS scenarios of the project.

The first industrial tests are expected to run in January 2020 following the erection phase.

3.4 Partnership of CLEANKER project

The CLEANKER consortium is an international partnership that integrates the research of 13 organizations:

Representatives from academia: Politecnico di Milano (Italy), Tallinn University of Technology (Estonia), Lappeenranta University of Technology (Finland); University of Stuttgart (Germany) and Tsinghua University (China);

Research centres: LEAP (Italy), CSIC (Spain) and VDZ (Germany);

SME: Quantis (Switzerland);

Technology provider: IKN (Germany);

End users: Buzzi Unicem and Italcementi – Heidelberg Group (Italy);

Environmental organization: Amici della Terra (Italy).

Thus providing all the necessary expertise and access to the industrial facilities to achieve the ambitious aim of the project.

The project is coordinated by LEAP, a non-profit research company in participation with the Politecnico di Milano which pursues effective Academia-Industry interaction in the field of Energy and the Environment.

5. STRATEGY OF CLEANKER PROJECT WITH RESPECT TO OTHER PATHWAYS FOR CO₂ REDUCTION

The cement industry is deeply engaged in the development of technology for CO₂ capture however a significant amount of work is also being carried out with the aim of reducing CO₂ at the material level. It is generally accepted that in spite of increasing constraints regarding environmental regulations (NO_x reduction, heavy metals) and issues regarding CO₂ emissions and environmental protection in terms of natural material deployment Portland cement remains and will remain over the coming decades one of the most commonly produced materials in the world. Several reasons support this hypothesis. First of all modern cement plants built according the BAT guidelines are based on a very efficient production process, able to minimize energy costs thanks to modern process technologies, automation and the use of alternative fuels without affecting the quality of the materials produced (clinker and cements). Secondly, Portland cement is a real “globalized industrial material” produced locally; in fact, although it is produced using different “primary” raw materials (limestone, clay, silica, coal) Portland cement can be considered as being very similar around the world in terms of performance, properties and composition, giving a high level of confidence to the users, also resulting from more than an hundred years of technical experience.

Moreover, cement with high limestone and low clinker content has already been extensively studied and verified in concrete. High limestone cement (examples CEM II B-LL, up to 35% weight of limestone) have been admitted by the EN 197-1 and authorized within Europe, moreover their use in structural concrete is limited in some countries due to concerns regarding higher carbonation depth and poor freeze thaw resistance when de-icing salt is present, Calcined clays are also often proposed as valid SCMs; the use of calcined clays is already authorized by EN 197-1 as a pozzolanic material up to 35%; the only requirement is on the content of reactive SiO₂ must be higher than 25%. A significant number of studies support their use [Scrivener K., 207], describing good performance in terms of strength and durability, however the economic and environmental convenience of this kind of material is strongly related to the local availability and to the presence of calcination facilities.

CSA cements have been known for a decade but only in the last year have they received significant attention from the cement industry. They are often proposed as an environmentally friendly alternative to OPC thanks to the lower CO₂ emissions associated with the production process and to the smaller amount of limestone required in the raw meal preparation [Aranda M. 2013]. LCA analysis performed during the production of CSA cement on an industrial scale shows that the CO₂ associated with the production process is much lower compared to OPC [Canonico F. 2016, Hanein T., 2018)].

Cement based on high Belite clinker (C₂S) has been extensively studied in the past [Stark K. 1987] and its production feasibility was also tested in an industrial clinker kiln [Popescu CD. 2003]. High Belite clinker is produced using the same raw materials available for Portland clinker production but with a lower lime saturation factor (LSF) compared to that used in OPC production. The burning

temperature of the high Belite clinker is also lower (1250 - 1350°C vs 1500°C for OPC) and the mineralogical composition highlights the low amount of C₃S (0 – 30%) and the high amount of C₂S (40 – 70%). It is well known that the hydraulic form of C₂S can be obtained only by very fast cooling or by chemical doping.

The interest in high Belite cement is not only related to its potential to save energy and CO₂ during the process of clinker production but also to other factors that could play a role in the economy of a cement plant. In fact, the production of a high Belite clinker could be an interesting solution for cement plants lacking good quality limestone and consequently accepting raw meal with lower LSF, moreover the upcoming stricter regulations related to NO_x emissions could also force some cement plants to lower the burning temperature of the clinker thus significantly reducing the NO_x emissions and producing a clinker with higher C₂S content. Future trends may also lead to an increase in the costs of SCMs such as fly ash or slag, making the use of an own made low heat clinker interesting to be used alone or in blends with OPC for casting massive concrete.

The demonstration of a technological solution for CCS or the development of innovative binders with reduced CO₂ at material level are completely different approaches in terms of technology complexity and output.

- a) CCS is currently being investigated as a future technology solution that could be applied to any industrial clinker production process for the removal and transportation of CO₂. The social acceptance and the infrastructure limit (CO₂-pipelines) are barriers that will need significant support from governments to be overcome.
- b) New clinkers (with intrinsically lower CO₂ emissions) are currently produced to satisfy the new demand from market such as high early strength cement (CSA) or low heat cement (belite clinker). They are nowadays produced on the basis of market requirements that are not dependent on their environmental friendliness
- c) Composite cements (acc. to EN 197-1) meets cement standards and allows savings of the clinker factor thus reducing the amount of clinker that is produced and, consequently, the CO₂ emitted. This is a technologically simple solution but the main barriers to a wider implementation are market acceptance and the durability requirement of a clinker factor lower than 50%

Table 1 reports some comparative data between a traditional production of Portland clinker, the hypothetical production of Portland clinker with a plant equipped with CCS technology based on Ca-L, an industrial production of CSA clinker and an industrial production of Belitic clinker. The data referring to Ca-L was obtained during the simulations performed during the CEMCAP project, the data of the CSA and Belitic clinker was based on real data extracted from short industrial tests.

The CO₂ emission values reported in the table account for both direct and indirect emission. The specific consumption is given in terms of primary energy, a quantity which allows to consistently take into account both thermal and electric consumptions.

The main results of this simulation can be summarized as follows:

- a) The CO₂ capture plant allows to dramatically decrease the CO₂ emissions (-89% compared to OPC), while still producing OPC. However, the capture process is energy intensive, so it causes an increase in the primary energy consumed by the whole plant - mainly given by an increase in the fuel need – as highlighted by the SPECCA index (Specific Primary Energy Consumption for CO₂ Avoided). This increase also leads to an increase in the CO₂ produced, hence 997.1 kgCO₂ have to be stored per t clinker.
- b) The production of an alternative clinker such as belitic or CSA clinker has an immediate effect on CO₂ emissions, with a reduction of approximately 20-25% with respect to the Portland clinker production process. The considered alternative clinkers also feature a lower primary energy consumption compared to OPC, as highlighted by the negative values of the SPECCA index.
- c) The production of CSA clinker have an higher impact on costs than CCS with Ca-L (in terms of delta production cost compared to OPC), and it features a significantly lower CO₂ emission reduction: this leads to a significantly higher Cost for CO₂ Avoided (CCA), the main indicator to compare CO₂ reduction strategies from an economic viewpoint. Belitic clinker can be produced with a similar cost compared to Portland clinker but with lower CO₂ emissions, which lead to a very attractive CCA value of 0 € per ton of CO₂ avoided. Hence, an immediate saving of CO₂ is noted but it can be valorised only if the performance of Belitic clinker is in the same order of magnitude as the Portland cement.

	Delta production cost compared to OPC	Specific CO ₂ emission (direct + indirect emission)	Specific primary energy consumption (direct + indirect emission)	SPECCA**	CCA***
	€/t clinker	Kg CO ₂ /t clinker	MJ l _h v /t clinker	MJ l _h v/kg CO ₂	€/t CO ₂
OPC Clinker	-	899,7	4,926	-	-
OPC Clinker (CC)	47	102,7	7,458	3,178	59
CSA Clinker	80	734,5	4,361	-3,421	485
Belitic Clinker	0	734,5	4,361	-3,421	0

(*) Fixed cost (direct costs of production – raw materials, fuels, energy)

(*) Specific primary energy consumption for CO₂ avoided

(**) Cost for CO₂ avoided

Table 1 Alternative clinker based cement

Table nr.2 shows the comparisons of a limestone Portland cement, produced with 80% Clinker and 20% limestone (CEM II A LL), a slag cement produced with 30% slag and 70% clinker (CEM III/B) and three corresponding composite cements produced by blending 80% CSA cement Next Base SR03 ¹ with 20% limestone (CSA II LL), 80% Belitic clinker cement with 20% limestone (BEL II LL), and 40% CSA cement Next Base SR03, 40% Belitic clinker with 20% limestone (CSA BEL II LL) respectively.

Looking at cement levels the situation is completely different. Portland cement is a unique material able to give the mortar very high strength and durability. Moreover, the blending of Portland cement with other supplementary cementitious material (SCMs) is also possible without interfering with the long term performance. Composite cements have also been admitted to the standard and are widely used.

Composite cement containing less than 30% of Portland clinker is able to reach the minimum strength requirement set by the standards and reduces the amount of CO₂ emitted or captured. A CEM III/B cement emits less than 300 kg CO₂ per ton of cement and with the hypothesis that the CO₂ emitted can be captured the *extra cost for the capturing process* remains in a cost range that could probably be afforded by the mortar and concrete industry.

The use of CSA cement have a highly significant impact on cost therefore it can only be taken into consideration for application where high early strengths are required.

Belitic cement is an innovative product still under investigation especially regarding its behaviour in combination with SCMs. Moreover the lower CO₂ emitted during its production process will probably make CO₂ capture with the Ca-L technology economically less favourable.

Anyway, it is important to notice that, even if some alternative cements may achieve non negligible CO₂ emission savings at very low cost, their adoption may be not sufficient to reach the Paris Agreement goals. In fact, CCS is the only technology which is able to abate the CO₂ emission below 100 kgCO₂/t cement.

¹ The CSA cement consists of a blend of 80% CSA clinker and 20% of Anhydrite.

	Strengths Class 2 days (MPa)	Strengths Class 28 days (MPa)	CO ₂ emitted (kg CO ₂ /t cement)	CO ₂ captured (kg CO ₂ /t cement) (**)	Delta production cost compared to reference (€/t cement) (*)	CCA (***) (€/t CO ₂)
CEM I (100% K)	30	52.5	900	0	-	-
CEM II A LL (Ca-L) (80% K, 20% LL)	20	42.5	100	900	37	46
CEM III/B (30% K, 70% S)	10	42.5	270	0	0	0
CEM III/B (Ca-L) (*) (30% K, 70% S)	10	42.5	30	276	14	16
BEL II LL (80% K-bel, 20% LL)	10	42.5	587	0	0	0
CSA II LL (80% CSA, 20% LL)	30	42.5	470	0	64	149
CSA BEL II LL (Ca-L) (*) (40% CSA, 40% K-bel, 20% LL)	20	42.5	527	0	32	86

(*) The delta production cost of CSA cement is assumed 80 €/t compared to CEM I;

(**) The efficiency of CO₂ capture is 94%;

(***) Cost for CO₂ avoided

Table 2 Comparison between CCS alternative solutions

At last, Figure 3 shows the effect of a 'carbon tax' on the delta cement production cost compared to the reference case (i.e. CEM I, without CCS and without any tax on CO₂). It has to be noticed that, for our purpose, a carbon tax is a generic cost associated to the emission of a ton of CO₂, hence it could also be seen as the value of the Emission Allowances on the EU Emission Trading Scheme. The Figure 3 consider a simplified scenario, where CAPEX, CO₂ transport and storage cost are not considered; moreover the possible costs variation associated to the availability of SCMs (slag), the possible optimisation of the production cost of CSA cement, the durability aspects, are also not taken into account.

The main results of this analysis are:

- a) The economic impact of Carbon Capture can be envisaged as positive when carbon tax reach 60 €/t
- b) The economic impact of Belitic cement production compared to a CEM II A LL cement can be envisaged as positive when carbon tax reach 80 €/t
- c) The economic impact of binder based on CSA cement, compared to a CEM I cement can be envisaged as positive when carbon tax reach > 90 €/t

Fig. 3 The effect of a carbon tax on the delta cement production cost compared to the reference case

6.1 Conclusion

The European cement industry is very involved in the development of innovative technologies for carbon capture and storage as well as for the production of hydraulic binders characterized by high performance and lower CO₂ emissions.

In spite of the new clinkers that have appeared on the market recently, and are characterized by innovative properties and lower CO₂ emissions compared to Portland clinker, Portland cement will remain over the next few years the major binder used in the world thanks to its well-known properties in terms of performance and durability.

Considering an average cost of 47 eur/t for Carbon Capture using the Ca-L process the final cost of CO₂ capture will be affordable for a composite cement containing a small amount of Portland clinker; the direct use of CSA cement has a higher impact on the cost in the end.

CSA clinker allows to save more than 15% of CO₂ during the production process, but it leads to a significant increase on both clinker cost (more expensive raw material) and cement cost (lower possibility to reduce the clinker factor).

The production of Belitic clinker is more environmentally friendly than Portland Clinker and a binder based on Belitic Clinker is under investigation as a possible alternative to Portland Cement. However the slower kinetics of hydration compared to Portland cement seems to limit the possibilities to use Belitic Clinker in combination with SCMs.

Moreover, the hypothetical cost for CO₂ capture from the production processes of a belitic or CSA clinker needs to be investigated since the lower CO₂ emissions of these clinkers compared to OPC could affect the efficiency of the capture process; Consequently, for these types of clinker different capture technologies and different capture levels may be more competitive, allowing for an optimization of operational and capital costs.

CCS with Ca-L seems to be a promising solution especially when the cement industry will have reached a low clinker ratio at the cement level, however in order to be implemented at an industrial level several barriers will have to be overcome:

- a) the social acceptance of CO₂ storage
- b) the possibility to retro-fit the capture technology on an existing cement plant
- c) the evaluation and optimisation of the capital costs of the capture unit for existing and new cement plants
- d) the implementation of composite and alternative clinker based cement with regards to standardisation, durability, and application in concrete

The CLEANKER project is an example of a very successful working group where industry, academia and institutions work together to develop new knowledge, building the infrastructure of a cement plant, creating awareness within the society to enable the acceptance of a new technology and assessing the impact of this technology compared to other pathways dealing with the material.

Besides the building of a demonstration plant based on Ca-L technology at the Buzzi Unicem plant in Vernasca (Italy – PC) CLEANKER will also approach the impact of CCS on the cement industry thus comparing other technologies for CCS and other pathways for CO₂ reduction.

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